

VERSATILE LAB-SCALE TEST RIG FOR EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS AND HEAT TRANSFER MODELLING OF THERMALLY ACTIVATED BUILDING SYSTEMS

Running title: TABS experimental lab-scale analysis and modelling

Tejero-González, Ana*¹; Velasco-Gómez, Eloy¹; Andrés-Chicote, Manuel², Rey-Martínez, Francisco Javier¹

¹ University of Valladolid, School of Engineering, Department of Energy Engineering and Fluidmechanics, Paseo del Cauce n.59, 47011, Valladolid, Spain

² CARTIF Technology Center, Parque Tecnológico de Boecillo, 205, 47151 Boecillo, Valladolid, Spain

*Corresponding author e-mail: anatej@eii.uva.es

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Abstract

Thermally Activated Building Systems (TABS) constitute an energy efficient building conditioning solution through the combination of low-exergy space heating and cooling and Thermal Energy Storage (TES) features. Their implementation is, however, complex, due to the number of factors involved in their design and operation. Mathematical models are useful to overcome this, but require validation, while experimental setups to study sensible TES can be bulky and difficult to handle. In this work, a homogeneous concrete slab and a multilayer concrete-sand-gravel slab are built and activated with constant heat flow. Both slabs are experimentally tested and their thermal behaviour is modelled through a 1D Finite Difference Method (FDM). Results demonstrate that materials such as sand and gravel can be used to provide relevant experimental data for TABS heat transfer model validation through a versatile lab test rig. A 1D FDM proves to be a simple, accurate method to predict the thermal behaviour of the slabs during transient peaks in charging and discharging processes as well as during steady-state operation, given that most of the time absolute errors remain below the measurement uncertainty thresholds. Finally, this paper sets a basis to support future experimental work on sensible TES and provides data for further model validation.

Keywords

Thermally Activated Building Systems (TABS); Sensible Thermal Energy Storage; laboratory-scale slabs; Transient Heat Transfer; 1D Finite Difference Method.

Nomenclature

T: temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

M-T : predicted temperature through 1D FDM [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

q: heat flux [W/m^2]

x: spatial dimension [m]

t: time [s]

A: area [m^2]

\dot{q} : heat flux density [W/m^2]

k: thermal conductivity [$\text{W}/(\text{mK})$]

ρ : density [kg/m^3]

c_p : specific heat capacity [$\text{J}/(\text{kgK})$]

α : thermal diffusivity [m^2/s]

Fo: Fourier Number

Bi: Biot Number

SUBINDICES

a: air

n: node

m: last node in the mesh (surface)

i: instant

0: 1 cm from active layer

5: 5 cm from active layer

10: 10 cm from active layer

15: 15 cm from active layer (surface)

ACRONYMS

TES Thermal Energy Storage

BITES Building Integrated Energy Storage

TABS Thermally Activated Building Systems

FDM Finite Difference Method

1. Introduction

Storage is the key technology to establish an efficient coupling between energy sources and generation, conversion or distribution system, as well as between such energy systems and their particular end-use applications, thus allowing for a smart thermal management¹. In the building sector, the urge towards Zero Energy Buildings impels alternative heating and cooling systems that require minimum energy consumption. Thermal Energy Storage (TES) can favour a more efficient use of energy if implemented either upstream of the building heating and cooling delivery systems² or directly integrated within the very building structure, being the latter sometimes referred as Building Integrated Thermal Energy Storage (BITES)³.

Thermally Activated Building Systems (TABS) constitutes a specific typology of low-energy radiant heating and cooling terminal systems that exploits strong thermal coupling between the water circuit and the constructive structure of the building itself, in order to provide a combined solution for efficient indoor conditioning and sensible TES⁴. Radiant systems provide low-temperature heating and high-temperature cooling, whereas TES allows for load shifting. This turns into a more efficient use of energy sources and generation equipment such as heat pumps, solar collectors, waste heat, low temperature cooling towers, etc.⁵, and even enables the use of low-energy water sources, which are naturally available at temperature levels between the indoor and outdoor air conditions and can be directly used to efficiently activate the structure⁶.

Because of the time response, the design, operation analysis and control of these systems are complex. Romaní et al.⁷ noted that the main standards related to the design, sizing and control of TABS focused on the heating or cooling capacity and water conditions, and reviewed the existing literature to identify the most influencing parameters in the performance of TABS. Position of the slab, piping type, diameter and spacing; properties, thickness and position of the different layers; supplied water temperature or flow rate are factors that should be evaluated in the design and control, according to the climate conditions and the building thermal loads^{5,7-9}.

Mathematical models are flexible tools to develop design and operating solutions for any specific case. Among the wide range of existing models reviewed by Romaní et al.⁷, only numerical methods (Finite Element -FEM- or Finite Difference -FDM-) are considered by the authors to accurately describe heat transfer and storage in TABS, though their complexity leads to simplified models validated with either numerical methods or experimental measurements. Experimental facilities are difficult to implement: real scale prototypes are influenced by too many factors and monitoring systems belonging to real buildings may imply measurement challenges. Consequently, “laboratory scale” slabs tested under appropriately controlled operating conditions are a simpler solution to obtain the required experimental results. With this aim, some researchers have built laboratory facilities to characterise different designs of slabs.

1.1. Existing experimental research

Experimental research has been conducted to characterise the thermal behaviour of slabs making use of measuring temperature probes within. Hawila et al.¹⁰ use 12 thermocouples to study the performance of a 5.6 cm insulation and a 4 cm anhydrite water-activated slab when working in two different modes: operating to achieve a room temperature of 20°C or changing this setpoint from 20°C to 23°C. Results allow them validating a model to predict the effect on the slab surface temperature, dissipated heat flow dissipated and room temperature when changing the water inlet temperature to the slab and the room temperature setpoint. As future work, they propose the application of the system to a room including the effect of solar radiation.

Comparison of 4 cases combining sensible and latent heat storage materials with two different piping is studied by Zhou&He ¹¹ aiming at releasing the heat as slowly as possible. Their experimental setup consists of a 120 mm reinforced concrete base layer, a 50 mm polystyrene insulation layer, the active layer with either a PE coil or a capillary mat, embedded on a sensible or latent thermal mass layer of 16 to 26 mm thicknesses depending on the case study and, finally, a 16 mm surface layer of wood board. It had seven T-type thermocouples at each of four levels: one on the insulation layer, one inside at half-thickness position, one into the heat storage material and one on the wood board. Results showed that a capillary mat provided more uniform temperature profile and a quicker response, while Phase Change Materials (PCM) released heat during double the time than sand.

With the opposite purpose of enabling intermittent operation of the radiant heating, Thomas et al. ¹² built a radiant floor with low thermal inertia which they called “light” floor and modelled it for comparison against a 80 mm concrete floor. They only developed experiments for the “light” radiant floor, hence without TES. They succeeded in validating their model under dynamic operation but provided less conclusive results in steady state mode.

Karlsson ¹³ validated a numerical model with experimental data from a water-activated heating floor placed on a test bench inside an insulated, ventilated chamber. The test bench enabled different floor constructions and pipe circuiting. Results were validated for a 3x3 m² floor consisting of 60 mm extruded polystyrene layer, 15 mm upon which were attached 7 U-shaped 5.7 m long pipes with inner 13 mm and outer 16 mm diameter. On top, the floor had a non-covered 60 mm concrete slab. Comparison to experimental measurements during cycles of 16 h and 8 h demonstrated that the model underestimated the steady-state heat flux by 16%, while temperatures were accurately predicted on the surface and underestimated by 0.3 to 1.5°C in the middle of the concrete slab. Tian et al. ¹⁴ studied the surface heat flux from the dynamic response of a concrete radiant cooling slab to validate a resistance-capacitor model. The slab consist of 20 mm polystyrene and 100 mm concrete with water pipes embedded at 40 mm depth. Five temperatures were measured on the upper surface, at 20 mm and 40 mm depth, and finally at each surface of the insulation layer. They obtained relative errors between the model and the experiments of 2% and 7% in steady and unsteady conditions, respectively.

Distancing from the particular application, but of use as references for the present work, are the experimental research developed by Nordbeck et al. ¹⁵ and Sacharczuk&Taler¹⁶, both related to TES for hot water supply. The former authors design a cement based solid-liquid heat storage system for hot water supply. They characterize its storage behaviour under different cycles and boundary conditions, achieving good agreement between experimental and simulated temperatures and heating rates. The latter propose and construct a water tank with an auxiliary concrete storage module, modelling the transient heat conduction through a Control Volume Finite Element Method instead of traditional Finite Element Method. Their methodology results appropriate for ceramic or concrete heat storage elements.

An alternative prototype of a slab provided with an air cavity is built by Wang et al. ¹⁷ and tested inside a climate chamber. The slab has insulation under the pipes and along its lateral surface, with no thermal mass between the active layer and the upper surface, but air. Temperature is measured on the surface of the active layer and on the upper and lower floor surfaces; the heat flux is measured on the surface of the floor. This prototype achieved enhanced heat transfer through convection from the surface, and the numerical simulation incurred into errors lower than 9%.

Concerning air activated slabs, many research has been conducted despite the complexity related to their thermal behaviour, as reviewed by Xu et al. ¹⁸. However, they found that some experimental works did not reveal details of the experiments. Among those who provide more extensive experimental results are Ren&Wright ¹⁹. They studied four commercial hollow core concrete slabs on a test room, characterising the thermal behaviour by measuring the temperatures inside the ventilated cores and within the concrete mass at 70 mm and 210 mm depth from the upper surface, but give no description about the positioning of the temperature sensors within. Their model provided acceptable accuracy for usual operating conditions but registered maximum errors of 4.2°C for the indoor temperature during brief periods at the beginning of the system operation.

As an alternative structure, Özrahat&Ünalán ^{20,21} built and characterised a concrete hollow column. To study its performance as a sensible TES and heater, the authors measured the airflow temperature and velocity, as well as the surface temperatures in 12 points, though not within the concrete mass. They concluded that the system could be used for building heating, but proposed and validated a 3D Computational Fluid Dynamics model to overcome the difficulties entrained in the experimental testing of the system. They also remarked the need for studying the thermal fatigue of the concrete column.

Lapka&Jaworski²² numerically investigated a hollowed ceiling panel made of gypsum mortar with microencapsulated PCM, of 1.5 cm thickness and 3 m length. Approached for summer conditions in Warsaw, it enabled precooling of ambient air that flows through U-shaped channels within the panel. They focused their study on the selection of the optimal gypsum-microencapsulated PCM composite depending on the working temperature ranges, for two different air velocities. The use of electrical resistance wires or mats to activate slabs is useful at a laboratory scale to provide a constant heat flow. Some experimental works actually resort to electrically activated slabs to study the use of Phase Change Materials (PCMs) for enhanced TES ²³⁻²⁶.

Chinnasamy&Appukuttan²⁷ successfully maintain indoor thermal comfort levels with reduced energy needs, through combination of conventional air-conditioning with latent heat thermal TES. Despite the enhanced load shifting achievable through latent heat storage, the use of PCMs can be an over-engineered solution for some applications. Because the simplest thermal energy storage relies on exploiting the very building structure as thermal reservoir, the characterization of the dynamic thermal behaviour of the concrete material is crucial. However, experimental results comparing sensible to latent TES lean towards the use of alternative materials for simplicity of the experimental facility ^{11,26}. Mathematical models are a practical alternative for such studies, but they still require validation.

When experimentally studying sensible TES, Zhou&He ¹¹ proposed the use of sand to change the layers easily; also Barrio et al. ²⁶ resorted to the same material to facilitate modifying the depth of the layout. However, none of these works explain the origin of the thermophysical properties considered for the sand. Moreover, despite the practicality of using other materials for sensible TES such as sand, there exists no research approaching how to extrapolate results from these laboratory scale alternatives to the study of the thermal behaviour of concrete slabs.

1.2. Scope of the work

The need for justifying the use of other materials rather than concrete for experimentally studying TES arises within this framework with the aim of enabling the construction of more versatile test

benches. These would facilitate the modification of the above key parameters when designing TABS, such as the thickness of the slab or the type and position of the heat source.

This work proposes the use of sand and gravel as an alternative to concrete in laboratory scale tests. With the aim of giving evidence for its use, the study targets the following objectives:

- Provide experimental data from a concrete and a multilayer sand-gravel slab.
- Validate a simple 1D FDM adapted to each slab.
- Identify the potential and limitations related to experimentation and model validation through sand-gravel slabs.

The article structure is as follows: Section 2 describes the experimental setup built and the methodology followed to perform the experiments; Section 3 develops the numerical 1D finite element difference method that describes the theoretical dynamic heat transfer in the system; Section 4 presents and compares the experimental results against the expected theoretical behaviour; and finally, the main results are highlighted in the conclusions.

2. Experimental procedure

2.1 Experimental setup

The experimental study aims at two targets: the first one is the characterization of the thermal response of concrete when reacting to heat charge and discharge; the second is to give evidence of the possibility of using other materials rather than concrete when studying the possibilities of sensible heat storage. The former target is achieved through the analysis of a $1 \times 1 \text{ m}^2$ surface, 15 cm thick, concrete slab. This slab is called C15 and is compared with a further slab called G15, which is a 15 cm multi-layered slab composed of 5 cm concrete and 10 cm of a sand and gravel mixture. Figure 1 shows views of both slabs at different stages of the construction of the experimental setup, where the left picture of figure 1.b. shows the 5 cm thick concrete layer in G15.

Table 1 gathers the properties of the different materials used in this work and the values expected from the literature. Because expected properties for concrete varied within a wide range, thermal conductivity, density and specific heat capacity have been measured for completely dry concrete, corresponding to the 5 cm thick concrete slab. Density of the 15 cm sand and gravel slab is also a measured value and served to determine the thermal conductivity and heat capacity according to the ranges provided by the literature.

Measurement of properties has been performed on a sample of $17 \times 21 \times 5 \text{ cm}^3$. Thermal conductivity of completely dried concrete has been obtained for the sample placed on the surface of a thermal box, by measuring the temperature on the two faces and the heat flux through the sample width. Specific heat capacity is measured with a calorimeter. Characteristics of the sensors used are described later in this section.

As shown in Figure 1, the bottom and lateral surfaces of the slabs are insulated with 8 cm of expanded polystyrene to favour 1D conduction from the active layer to the upper surface. The active layer consists of an electric resistance wire arranged on a wood board with 9 cm spacing. An aluminium plate placed upon the wire arrangement enables uniform heat transfer from the active layer, which was checked through a thermal imaging camera. This setup provides a constant, uniform 155 W heat flux that enables plain experimental results for model validation.

Figure 2 shows a scheme of each slab plan and cross section, identifying the measuring sensors used and their position. Four temperatures are measured in both slabs at 5 and 10 cm above the active layer and upon the upper surface, at the intersection points of a 3x3 grid. Besides these measuring points, there is a heat flux meter placed in the middle of the surface. Construction of slab C15 enabled a further temperature sensor 0.5 cm above the active layer at the axis of symmetry of the slab.

Temperature sensors used are four wire Pt100 with range from -50 to 250°C and accuracy $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$. The heat flux meter has temperature stability between -40 and 80°C; calibrated value $< 15 \text{ W/m}^2$ with accuracy of 5% at 23°C.

Temperature measuring at several points of each layer permits identification of the uncertainty introduced by the position of the sensor. Maximum standard deviation observed in the values measured is 0.18, 0.28 and 0.44 for layers at 5, 10 and 15 cm respectively, hence possibly related to the relevance of the border effect introduced by the upper surface.

The slabs are placed horizontally on the floor inside a climate chamber for their characterization as radiant floor heating structures. This chamber (Figure 3) is located inside the laboratory, elevated 0.36 m above the floor.

The dimensions of the climate chamber are 4x4x3 m. The walls are 40 mm polystyrene sandwich panels with 0.6 mm steel plating. It has one door of dimensions 0.82x2.04 m and four windows of 0.9x1.4 m each, double-glazed 4/8/4. Total glazed area is 6.7 m^2 . It is equipped with a heat pump to achieve the desired indoor thermal conditions.

To check that radiant asymmetry does not occur inside the climate chamber, it was equipped with three temperature sensors (Figure 3): one in the middle of the indoor space, above the target slab, and two surface probes placed on the inner wall at the back and on the inner surface of the front window. To avoid any variability of these surface temperatures, the ambient air of the laboratory where the climate chamber is placed was controlled and monitored with a fourth temperature sensor.

2.2 Tests and methodology

A total of seven experimental tests have been performed to provide data about the thermal behaviour of the slabs. During these tests, temperatures in the climate chamber, temperatures within the slabs thickness and heat flow dissipated from surface were monitored as described previously. Test conditions are described in Table 2.

Tests No.1 and 2 were designed to validate the 1D FDM for the concrete C15 slab under thermal charge and discharge until steady state. Tests are for two ambient temperatures, 20°C and 24°C. Validation of the model under these two conditions would enable its use under indoor thermal comfort in winter, considering a normal level of expectation with metabolic activity of 1.2 met and clothing insulation 1 clo²⁸.

Then, the model is checked for the multilayered slab G15 with tests No.5 to No.7. The acceptability of the same model applied to either slab would justify the use of further experimental results with sand and gravel slabs for future model validation. Section 4.1. presents the results of the model validation.

Then, the whole set of tests are aimed at reproducing typical experiments to be developed in laboratory scale slabs when studying the behavior of TABS. Once the model is validated, it is used to predict the behavior of slab G15 under 24°C of ambient air. Results are discussed in sections 4.2. for steady state mode and 4.3. for tests under peak charges. Comparison among

results for both slabs illustrates how to interpret future experimental tests performed on multilayered, more versatile slabs for studying the behavior of TABS.

3. Mathematical Model

Given the characteristics of the experimental setup (insulation on all edges of the slab with the exception of the upper surface), the dynamic thermal behaviour of the slab can be approximated by a 1D model – only heat flows in one direction: the normal direction to the active layer. One boundary condition establishes a constant heat flux and the other sets heat transfer through convection to the ambient air at a particular temperature.

The model in finite differences can be defined from an energy balance in a node n at a particular instant I (Figure 4). For a particular layer n , heat flow transferred from layer $n-1$ either can accumulate within n or transfer to the next $n+1$ layer.

Hence, for an internal node, provided that no heat generation exists:

$$-k \cdot \frac{T_n^i - T_{n-1}^i}{\Delta x} = -k \cdot \frac{T_{n+1}^i - T_n^i}{\Delta x} + \rho \cdot c_p \cdot \Delta x \cdot \frac{T_n^{i+1} - T_n^i}{\Delta t} \quad (E-1)$$

Where Δt is the time step and Δx the 1D spatial discretization of the slab. This expression (E-1) corresponds to the explicit finite-difference method^{29,30}. The temperature of a particular node at a particular time can be solved from the temperatures of that node and the two adjacent nodes at the time step before. A simple numerical model can thus be implemented in a spreadsheet by developing this expression for the slab discretised in Δx .

Expressed in terms of the Fourier number (E-2), we obtain expression (E-3):

$$Fo = \frac{\alpha \cdot \Delta t}{\Delta x^2} \quad (E-2)$$

$$T_n^{i+1} = T_n^i + Fo \cdot (T_{n+1}^i - 2T_n^i + T_{n-1}^i) \quad (E-3)$$

Alternatively:

$$T_n^{i+1} = Fo \cdot (T_{n+1}^i + T_{n-1}^i) + (1 - 2Fo)T_n^i \quad (E-4)$$

From where it can be deduced that this method, though simple, must meet the condition $(1 - 2Fo) > 0$ to avoid instability of the calculus; then:

$$Fo < 1/2 \quad (E-5)$$

Otherwise, the temperature at a certain node would depend negatively on its temperature at the instant immediately before, thus generating oscillations in the numerical method. Because $Fo < 1/2$ implies that $\Delta t < \Delta x^2 / (2\alpha)$, then it physically represents the minimum time step required to allow heat to transfer within the selected discretization Δx .

Consequently, the selection of the time step Δt and the discretization Δx , hence the Fourier number, is critical due to the stability condition, the accuracy achievable and the required computation time.

3.1. Boundary conditions

One of the boundary conditions of the FDM is the constant heat flux provided from the active layer (155W distributed uniformly from a 1m^2 surface):

$$\dot{q} = -k \cdot \frac{T_1^i - T_0^i}{\Delta x} + \rho \cdot c_p \cdot \frac{\Delta x}{2} \cdot \frac{T_0^{i+1} - T_0^i}{\Delta t} \quad (E-6)$$

This implies that, at node $n=0$ at any instant i :

$$T_0^{i+1} = 2Fo \cdot \left(\dot{q} \cdot \frac{\Delta x}{k} + T_1^i \right) + (1 - 2Fo) \cdot T_0^i \quad (E-7)$$

Where the stability condition remains the same (E-5).

The boundary condition at the upper surface of the slab implies heat dissipation to ambient air from the last node, m :

$$-k \cdot \frac{T_m^i - T_{m-1}^i}{\Delta x} = h \cdot (T_m^i - T_a) + \rho \cdot c_p \cdot \frac{\Delta x}{2} \cdot \frac{T_m^{i+1} - T_m^i}{\Delta t} \quad (E-8)$$

Thus, temperature of node m at instant $i+1$ would be in terms of Biot number:

$$Bi = \frac{h}{k} \cdot \Delta x$$

$$T_m^{i+1} = 2Fo \cdot (Bi \cdot T_a + T_{m-1}^i) + (1 - 2Fo - 2Bi \cdot Fo) \cdot T_m^i \quad (E-10)$$

Being the stability condition now restricted to the following:

$$Fo \cdot (1 + Bi) < 1/2 \quad (E-11)$$

The modelling of the dynamic heat transfer from the upper surface to the space through both convection and radiation requires definition of the total heat transfer coefficient. For simplicity, this model makes use of the expression proposed in the international standard. For the case of floor radiant heating ³¹:

$$\dot{q} = 8.92 \cdot (T_a - T_m)^{1.1} \quad (E-12)$$

However, it must be noted that a more precise study should approach the convection and radiation heat transfer coefficients separately, as recommended in previous research ³².

3.2. Stability conditions

Due to the boundary condition at the upper surface of the slab, the condition for the method stability depends on the Biot number (E-11). When Biot number is considerably small yet positive ($Bi < 0.1$), spatial effects can be disregarded. Despite not reaching such low values here, Biot number remains small due to the order of magnitude of the heat transfer coefficient in these applications (about $10 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\text{K})$), thus having little effect on the stability condition. Because anyway the value of the Bi would not become much lower than unity, a discretization method is still appropriate for modelling the thermal behaviour ³³.

Consequently, the selection of the Fo value within the range $(0, 1/2)$ ensures stability and determines the accuracy of the calculus. For a particular material, it will depend upon the selection of the time step and the spatial discretization. For a homogeneous material, which is the case of the C15 concrete slab, the selection of the differential thicknesses would be uniform. However, for a multilayer slab, typical of building walls, an alternative criterion can be the selection of a uniform “mesh ratio” (Fourier number), which requires an uneven discretization, as proposed by Waters&Wright ³⁴. Although this criterion has been considered less practical ³³, it has been used in later research work for comparison of numerical results to experimental measurements in multi-layered slabs ^{35,36}. Actually, it provided more accurate results than considering a uniform grid hence different Fourier numbers ³⁶. In present work, both criteria have been considered for the Finite Difference modelling of the concrete-grave and sand slab.

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Validation of the model

Firstly, the 1D FDM is implemented with a homogeneous 0.01m discretization. The selected Δx enables direct comparison to the experimental values in the model validation without introducing excessive computational effort. A time step of 12 s for the C15 homogeneous slab yields a constant Fo of about 0.115. For the multi-layered G15 slab and a time step chosen of 60 s, Fo is near 0.13 for the 5 cm concrete layer and near 0.24 for the 10 cm sand and gravel layer.

Validity of the model is analysed through the absolute error, in Celsius, between the measured and predicted temperatures at the target layers.

In this section, figure 5 to figure 9 show the evolution, at each layer, of measured (T_0, T_5, T_{10} and T_{15}) and predicted ($M-T_0, M-T_5, M-T_{10}$ and $M-T_{15}$) temperatures. Subfigures present the absolute error generated.

The model has been first validated with tests 1 and 2. Figure 5 presents results for the slab C15 under conditions of test No.1. The absolute error for layers at 5, 10 and 15 cm falls below the uncertainty due to the position of the sensor (0.18, 0.28 and 0.44, as given in section 2) during 40%, 29% and 67% of the time, respectively. Because it never exceeds 1°C for most of the time on the overall (99%, 97%, 86% and 96% for layers 0, 5, 10 and 15 cm), the method is considered acceptable. It must be noted that the accuracy of the method diminishes during the first stage of the thermal charge. The isolated peak of absolute error registered when the thermal discharge can be affected by the uncontrolled instability of the ambient temperature at that moment. It can thus be concluded that, on the overall, the model provides suitable values for the temperature profile evolution within homogeneous slabs.

The model provides also acceptable results for the slab under conditions of test No.2. In this case, the absolute error for layers at 5, 10 and 15 cm remain below the uncertainty of the sensor position during 63%, 67% and 69% of the time, respectively, in any case exceeding 1°C.

Figure 6 accounts for the G15 multilayer slab. In this case, the accuracy of the model clearly diminishes during the initial stage of heat discharge, as it overestimates the velocity of thermal charge and discharge.

To improve this, a modified 1D FDM using an uneven discretization, hence constant Fourier number, is proposed. The mesh defined in this case follows the strategy suggested by Waters and Wright³⁴. For a 60s time step and nodes placed at the internal boundary as well as at the two further layers where temperatures are measured (10 cm and 15 cm), the best discretization is 0.0125 cm for the concrete layer and 0.0167 cm for the sand and gravel one. This yields to a near constant Fourier number of 0.13 all throughout the slab thickness. It is interesting to note that this value is not far from the optimal Fourier number obtained by Bruzgevičius et al.³⁶; thus the accuracy achievable is expected to be enough.

Figure 7 corresponds to a constant Fo 1D FDM. This modification in the method softens the absolute error registered at the beginning of the thermal discharge. In addition, a constant Fo discretization with a node in the boundary between the concrete and the sand and gravel layers decrease the absolute error obtained in this position (5 cm) during thermal charge and stationary. The error between the measured and the predicted temperatures at the surface diminishes during this period, too.

However, predicted results at 10 cm (M-T10), the only position located within the sand and gravel layer, shift from the measured ones (T10). This denotes two facts: firstly, that the inhomogeneity of the material may be affecting the experimental results; secondly, that there exists further variability in the measurement beyond the uncertainty observed between the four probes in that position. This demonstrates the limitations of experimental measures within inhomogeneous, non-compact materials.

Figure 8 shows for the transient heat transfer in slab G15 during tests No. 6 and 7, provided a homogeneous discretization. The absolute error at 15 cm does not exceed the uncertainty of the measurement due to the position of the sensors during 99% of the test; however, for layers 5 and 10 cm it is restricted to these limits only during 15% and 25% of the time. Nonetheless, it remains under 0.5 during the whole test for layer 10 cm and during 90% of the time for layer 5 cm. The remaining 10% of the time when the error exceeds 0.5°C at 5 cm is due to the overestimation of the maximum temperatures achieved when the thermal discharge starts.

Comparison to results provided by a constant Fo 1D FDM shown in figure 9 leads to a similar conclusion to the one extracted from comparing figure 6 to figure 7. Firstly, the constant Fo mesh softens the peak error that occurs when the heat flux provided from the active layer stops. Moreover, results for the boundary layer 5 cm improve, remaining the error below the uncertainty during 85% of the test. However, there is no clear worsening of the results at layer 10 cm. Although in this case the error exceeds 0.5°C during 10% of the time (note peaks in figure 9), it stays under the uncertainty of the measure due to the sensor position for 88% of the time, hence globally improving.

Taking all this into account, a simple 1D FDM in an explicit form provides an accurate estimation of the evolution of the temperature profile within homogeneous slabs for sensible TES. A constant Fourier mesh softens the peak errors observed when the thermal discharge begins. However, the improvement achieved may not justify the complexity introduced by an uneven discretization, corroborating the remarks in existing research³³. On the other hand, enough accuracy of results obtained with the selected discretization justifies disregarding a smaller mesh, whose time step required for a Fourier within the stability limits would yield excessive computational effort.

4.2. Thermal behaviour until stationary.

Table 3 gathers the measured and predicted temperature profiles reached by each slab when thermally charged until stationary, under 20°C and 24°C of ambient air. Experimental results belong to tests No. 1, 2 and 5, while predicted values are obtained with 1D FDM for homogeneous discretization.

Table 4 presents the times it takes both slabs to reach steady state, during thermal charge and discharge. Times registered for slab G15 are longer due to its thermophysical properties, hence larger thermal inertia. This last result yields an important conclusion when aiming at using sand and gravel for this sort of experimental setups: versatility improves in detriment of test times required.

4.3. Thermal behaviour under peak charges.

Once the heat transfer in the slabs is characterized until stationary, they have been tested under different peak charges in tests 3, 4, 6 and 7. Figure 10 shows the heat flow dissipated from both slabs when charged during 2 and 4h. For slab C15 under either 2 or 4h peak charge (tests No. 3 and 4), the maximum heat flow dissipated from the surface occurs one hour after the electric

resistance stops. This result agrees with the foreseeable independence of the thermophysical properties from the temperature at the operating conditions.

Figure 11.a represents the corresponding heat storage in the C15 slab along the operating time for the same tests No. 3 and 4. The decrease represented in the graph once the charging period is finished corresponds to the values of heat flow dissipated from the surface measured with the heat flux meter. Consequently, in the particular ambient conditions the slab is able to dissipate from its surface half the heat storage during the next 6h10min and 7h45min after a 2h and 4h peak charge, respectively.

For slab G15, the maximum heat dissipated occurs 3h50min after the stop of the electric resistance, for both 2 and 4h peak charge (tests No. 6 and 7), as shown in figure 10. Regarding figure 11.b, the slab dissipates from its surface half the heat stored after 10h50min (2h peak charge – test No. 6) and 15h15min (4h peak charge – test No. 7).

Due to their different thermal inertia, experimental measurements from other materials rather than concrete cannot be considered directly for designing TABS, though can be used to validate a model. However, surface temperatures measured in experimental tests with G15 can be used to predict achievable ones in concrete slabs. Besides, heat accumulated within the slabs is of the same order of magnitude under short charge periods (2h).

Despite the larger test times required, which can increase from 50 to 80% the times required for concrete slabs to reach 90% of total thermal charge and discharge, the use of laboratory scale slabs such as G15 has several advantages. These more versatile experimental benches can facilitate the building of the slab, in addition to the modification of parameters such as the thickness of the slab or the position of the active layer, key factors for the design of TABS.

5. Conclusions

This work presents the experimental thermal behaviour of activated slabs composed of different sensible Thermal Energy Storage (TES) materials and compares it to the theoretical results. It aims at validating the use of more versatile laboratory scale slabs, setting a basis for future research on mathematical models or experimentation with variable heat flux. The main findings are:

- Comparison between measured and predicted values through a 1D Finite Difference Method (FDM) demonstrate that a simple model of this type can be adequate to predict the transient thermal behaviour of homogeneous activated slabs for TES, avoiding the need for resorting to methods whose complexity limits their applicability.
- The 1D FDM is easily adaptable to a multilayer sand-gravel slab. Modelling through an uneven discretization, yielding a constant Fourier number, introduces further complexity in the model without entraining clear improvement in the predicted results.
- Using sand and gravel in laboratory scale slabs has the limitations of stretching the test times required and the need for carefully placing the temperature sensors within.
- Surface temperatures achieved on either concrete or sand and gravel slabs coincide. Thus, direct use of experimental results in sand and gravel slabs is possible when characterizing surface operating conditions of real TABS.
- As expected, temperature gradient within the slabs differ, though does not impede the use of experimental results with sand and gravel slabs to validate mathematical models.

Consequently, the use of other materials rather than concrete is justified for studying sensible TES in easily modifiable test benches at a laboratory scale, aiming at providing experimental data to model the thermal behaviour of Thermally Activated Building Systems.

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Table 1. Thermal properties of materials.

	Thermal conductivity	Density	Specific heat capacity
	k [W/(mK)]	ρ [kg/m ³]	c_p [J/(kgK)]
Concrete (Hensen&Nakhi ³³)	1.9	2300	840
Mortar (Joulin et al. ³⁷)	0.665 (12-20°C)	2001	915 (11.4-19.4°C)
	0.648 (32-40°C)		936 (32-40°C)
Concrete (Ünalán&Özrahat ²¹)	2.1	2400	960
Reinforced concrete (Zhou&He ¹¹)	1.74	2500	920
Concrete (Song et al. ³⁸)	2.01	2440	NA
Concrete (Thomas et al. ¹²)	1.8	2300	1000
Concrete (Thieblemont et al. ³⁹)	2.25	2200	990
Concrete (Karlsson ¹³)	1.5	2300	920
Air dried concrete at 20°C (Raznjevic ⁴⁰)	0.186-1.105	500-2250	795-879
Completely dry concrete at 20°C (Raznjevic ⁴⁰)	0.128-0.837	500-2250	795-879
Gravel at 20°C (Raznjevic ⁴⁰)	0.93	1500-1800	879
Sand, average at 20°C (Raznjevic ⁴⁰)	0.93	1500-1800	712
Sand (Zhou&He ¹¹)	NA	1600	1050
Concrete, completely dry (Present study, 5 cm slab)	0.61 (45°C) †	2160 †	830 †
Concrete (Present study, 15 cm slab)	2	2310 †	900
Sand and gravel (Present study)	0.93	1777 †	835

NA: Data not available at the reference cited.

† Measured values

Table 2. Experimental tests performed.

Test No.	Slab	Mode
1	C15	Steady state (Charge – discharge at Ta=20 °C).
2	C15	Steady state (Charge – discharge at Ta=24 °C).
3	C15	Transitory (2 h peak charge – discharge).
4	C15	Transitory (4 h peak charge – discharge).
5	G15	Steady state (Charge – discharge at Ta=20 °C).
6	G15	Transitory (2 h peak charge – discharge).
7	G15	Transitory (4 h peak charge – discharge).

Table 3. Average temperature profiles in stationary.

Slab	Layer	Ta=20°C		Ta=24°C	
		Experimental	Model	Experimental	Model
C15	T 15	33.6	33.9	37.4	38.1
	T 10	38.3	37.8	41.5	41.9
	T 5	41.7	41.6	45.5	45.7
	T 0	44.4	44.7	48.7	48.8
G15	T 15	34.7	34.5	-	37.3
	T 10	44.3	42.7	-	46.9
	T 5	53.2	52.8	-	57.2
	T 0	-	65.5	-	67.4

Table 4. Times (in hours) required for charge until 50%, 90% and 99% stationary and discharge until 50%, 10% and 1% stationary at 20°C ambient temperature.

Slab	Charge times until stationary [h]			Discharge times until stationary [h]		
	50%	90%	99%	50%	10%	1%
C15	5.35	15.27	22.76	6.58	19.5	21.66
G15	8.75	23.61	46.78	17.61	35.94	56.84

Figure legends

Figure 1. Views of the (a) C15 and (b) G15 slabs at different stages of construction.

Figure 2. Plan view and cross section system configuration and sensor locations for (a) C15 and (b) G15.

Figure 3. View of the climate chamber and the positions of the temperature sensors.

Figure 4. Spatial discretization of the slab.

Figure 5. a) Test No.1 measured (T) and 1D FDM predicted (M-T) temperatures and b) absolute error.

Figure 6. a) Test No.5 measured (T) and 1D FDM predicted (M-T) temperature profiles and b) absolute errors (homogeneous discretization).

Figure 7. Test No.5 measured (T) and 1D FDM predicted (M-T) temperature profiles and b) absolute errors (uneven discretization - constant F_o).

Figure 8. a) Tests No.6 and 7 measured (T) and 1D FDM predicted (M-T) temperatures and b) absolute error (homogeneous discretization).

Figure 9. a) Tests No.6 and 7 measured (T) and 1D FDM predicted (M-T) temperatures and b) absolute error (uneven discretization - constant F_o).

Figure 10. Heat flow dissipated from both slabs under 2 and 4h peak charges.

Figure 11. Heat stored in a) C15 and b) G15 under 2 and 4h peak charges.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

(A)

(B)

Figure 6

(A)

(B)

Figure 7

(A)

(B)

Figure 8

(A)

(B)

Figure 9

(A)

(B)

Figure 10

Figure 11

(A)

(B)